

THE
SEGESTRIIDAE
OF
SOUTH AFRICA

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ABSTRACT

The family Segestriidae is represented by four genera and 136 species with a wide distribution. From South Africa a single genus *Ariadna* represented by 15 species are known. The genus has not yet been revised. For only two species *Ariadna corticola* Lawrence, 1952 and *Ariadna karrooica* Purcell, 1904 are known of both sexes. Five species are known only from the type locality all sampled prior to 1904. Twelve species are South African endemics and two southern African endemics. Seven of the 15 species are Data Deficient and more sampling is needed.

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CONTENTS

FAMILY SEGESTRIIDAE.....4

GENUS *ARIADNA* Audouin, 1826.....4

- *Ariadna bilineata* Purcell, 1904 5
- *Ariadna capensis* Purcell, 19046
- *Ariadna corticola* Lawrence, 19527-8
- *Ariadna dentigera* Purcell, 19049
- *Ariadna gryllotalpa* (Purcell, 1904)10
- *Ariadna hottentotta* Purcell, 190811
- *Ariadna insularis* Purcell, 190812
- *Ariadna jubata* Purcell, 190413
- *Ariadna karrooica* Purcell, 190414
- *Ariadna kolbei* Purcell, 190415
- *Ariadna lightfooti* Purcell, 190416
- *Ariadna scabripes* Purcell, 190417
- *Ariadna segestrioides* Purcell, 190418
- *Ariadna similis* Purcell, 190819
- *Ariadna umtalica* Purcell, 190420
- UNDETERMINED SPECIES.....21

REFERENCES.....22

Photos Victor Hamilton Atwell

Photo Elsa van Niekerk

Photo Allen Jones.

Examples of tube-webs

Female with egg sac Photo J. Young

FAMILY SEGESTRIIDAE –ARIADNA

The family Segestriidae is represented by four genera and 136 species (World Spider Catalog 2021) that have a wide distribution. From South Africa a single genus *Ariadna* represented by 15 species all endemic to southern Africa.

COMMON NAME: Segestriidae (tube-web spiders); *Ariadna* spp. (jack-in-a-box spider).

MORPHOLOGY: Body size: 6-15 mm (males very similar in size). Colour: body colour varies from yellowish brown to reddish black to purplish black abdomens without patterns or if present they consist of transverse bars. Carapace longer than wide with the fovea a small depression; hirsute to glabrous; eyes six in two rows all pale in colour; eyes positioned close to the clypeal edge; chelicerae free, long and slender; fangs small; cheliceral furrow with few teeth; endites longer than wide, well developed; labium much longer than wide (b); serrula well developed, in a single row. Abdomen longer than wide, cylindrical; hairy; spinnerets short; anterior spinnerets contiguous. Legs three-clawed with third pair of legs directed forwards with legs I and II; front legs with a double row of spines ventrally (d). Genitalia haplogyne (e).

LIFESTYLE: Construct a signal-web consisting of a silk tube that is closed at the bottom, with about a dozen dry silk trip lines radiating outwards from the open end of the tube (f); retreat: the spider use the tube part as a retreat. The tubes are made in crevices of walls, rocks, fallen tree trunks, bark of trees and in the soil. Some species are common in indigenous forest where they make their tube retreats in fallen wooden trunks, while others are adapt to drier and arid savanna, Nama-Karoo, Succulent Karoo and desert regions.

Ariadna spp. are nocturnal and the spiders are seen in the entrance of the tubes during the night with the tip of 6 legs visible on the rim of the tube. Prey movement is transmitted with vibrations to the spider from the radiating trip lines. The surprisingly swift reaction with which the spider strikes could be compared with that of a jack-in-the-box. The prey is seized and pulled instantly back into the tube. The double row of strong spines on the ventral surface of the front legs helps to grab and hold the prey. The third pair of legs directed forwards with legs I and II, help with the quick forward and backward movement of the spider in the tube. The entrance of the *Ariadna* tube has a small collar of very regular white silk. The trip lines have no adhesive elements and have only a signalling function.

TAXONOMY: The South African *Ariadna* species have not been revised. Fourteen of the species were described by Purcell (1904 and 1908).

Segestriidae. a: *Ariadna* sp., female, dorsal view; b: cephalothorax, ventral view; c: eye pattern, dorsal view; d: leg I, ventral view; e: male palp, lateral view; f: radiating tube-web (after Dippenaar-Schoeman & Jocqué 1997).

Ariadna bilineata Purcell, 1904

COMMON NAME: Signal Hill Tube-Web Spider / Side-striped Tube-Web Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described by Purcell (1904) from Table Mountain National Park, Signal Hill in the Western Cape. The species is sampled from four provinces (EOO=283 027 km²; AOO=56 km²; 5-1397 m a.s.l.). Although the species is presently known only from one sex it has a wide geographical range and can be listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Gauteng:** Faerie Glenn Nature Reserve (-25.7707, 28.3008). **Limpopo:** Blouberg Nature Reserve (-23.12, 29.00); Vhembe Biosphere Barries Farm (-22.4755, 29.4052); Vhembe Biosphere Ben Lavin Nature Reserve (-23.1426, 29.9452); Klein Kariba (-24.88, 28.29). **North West:** Hartbeespoortdam (-25.73, 27.85). **Western Cape:** Table Mountain National Park, Signal Hill (-33.9, 18.38); Table Mountain National Park, Devils Peak (-33.92, 18.45); Hottentots Holland Mountains (-34.07, 18.56); Paarl (-33.71, 18.98); Caledon (-34.24, 19.43); St. Helena Bay (-32.77, 18.03); Robben Island (-33.8076, 18.3712); Hermanus (-34.40, 19.25); Rawsonville (-33.70, 19.34).

LIFESTYLE: This species lives in tube signal-webs that are made in crevices of walls, rocks, fallen tree trunks or bark of trees. Sampled from the Fynbos and Savanna biomes (Foord et al. 2011).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no known threats to the species but the male still needs to be described. It is protected in Faerie Glenn Nature Reserve, Blouberg Nature Reserve (Muelelwa et al. 2010; Foord et al. 2019), Ben Lavin Nature Reserve and Table Mountain National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2020c).

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised, known only from the female. Carapace reddish-yellow to dark reddish-brown, darker anteriorly; surface hairy and usually finely veined with black; chelicera yellowish-red to black. Abdomen with a fine, pale yellow line running from end to end down middle. Legs faintly or strongly infuscated, the anterior pairs darker than the posterior ones. TL: 6-7.5 mm (Purcell 1904).

Ariadna bilineata from Klein Kariba Photo Peter Webb

***Ariadna capensis* Purcell, 1904**

COMMON NAME: Table Mountain Tube-Web Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Western Cape endemic described by Purcell (1904) from the Wynberg Hill, Table Mountain. Recent collections were made in the Cederberg Wilderness Area (EOO=1 890 km²; AOO=12 km²; 24-481 m a.s.l.). The status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species' range. Therefore, listed as Data Deficient for taxonomic reasons.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Western Cape:* Wynberg Caves, Table Mountain (-34.05, 18.45); Cederberg Wilderness Area, Sawadee 385 m a.s.l. (-32.337, 18.991); Cederberg Wilderness Area, Wupperthal, 531 m a.s.l. (-32.280, 19.219).

LIFESTYLE: This species lives in tube signal-webs that are made in crevices of walls, rocks, fallen tree trunks or bark of trees. Sampled from the Fynbos Biome.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Threats to the species are unknown. It is protected in the Cederberg Wilderness Area (Foord & Dippenaar-Schoeman (2016) and Table Mountain National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2020c).

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised, known only from the female. Carapace brownish-red, the head darker, especially in anterior region; chelicera reddish-black; labium dark brown, paler at apex; sternum reddish-brown. Legs reddish; front legs redder; first pair brownish-red, tibia and metatarsus darker; anterior femora infuscated along middle below and on distal part of inner surface. Abdomen purplish-black, with narrow yellow line on each side. Total length 9.25 mm (Purcell 1904).

Ariadna corticola Lawrence, 1952

COMMON NAME: Bow-legged Tube-Web Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described by Lawrence (1952) from Ingwavuma in KwaZulu-Natal. The species is sampled from five provinces occurring in more than 10 protected areas (EOO=346 238 km²; AOO=88 km²; 7-1690 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographical range, the species is therefore listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Grahamstown (-33.3, 26.52). **Free State:** Amanzi Private Game Reserve (-28.62, 26.68). **Gauteng:** Pretoria/Tshwane (-25.74, 28.19); Klipriviersberg Nature Reserve Site 1 (-26.3112, 28.0026); Klipriviersberg Nature Reserve Site 3 (-26.3075, 28.0147); Klipriviersberg Nature Reserve Site 5 (-26.2912, 28.0277); Irene (-25.868, 28.218). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Ingwavuma (-27.12, 32.01); iSimangaliso Wetland Park: Hell's Gate (-28, 32.48); Hluhluwe Nature Reserve (-28.09, 32.1); Ithala Nature Reserve (-27.51, 31.23); Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.87, 32.24); Ophathe Game Reserve (-28.52, 31.66); Tembe Elephant Park (-26.94, 32.47). iSimangaliso Wetland Park Eastern Shores Nature Reserve (-29.0954, 32.1573); iSimangaliso Wetland Park Gwala-Gwala Forest (-28.3840, 32.4073); iSimangaliso Wetland Park Mkhuzi Game Reserve (-27.6, 32.02); iSimangaliso Wetland Park uMkhuze Game Reserve A (-27.6093, 32.2273); iSimangaliso Wetland Park uMkhuze Game Reserve (-27.6568, 32.2676); iSimangaliso Wetland Park uMkhuze Game Reserve (-27.6593, 32.2703); Pongola (-27.38, 31.62). **Limpopo:** Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve, Farm Malta (-24.1617, 30.2538). **Mpumalanga:** Kruger National Park, Pretoriuskop, Numbi (-25.140, 31.208); Kruger National Park (-24.98, 31.58).

LIFESTYLE: This species lives in tube signal-webs that are made in crevices of walls, rocks, fallen tree trunks or bark of trees. The holotype female was taken under the bark of the fever tree *Vachellia xanthophloea*, the male in a nest below a fallen tree trunk in the same locality. Haddad (2016) sampled it again in the Ndumo Game Reserve (2016). Sampled from the Indian Ocean Coastal Belt, Forest, Grassland (Haddad et al. 2013), Savanna (Foord et al. 2011) and Thicket biomes.

Ariadna corticola female from Irene Photo Peter Webb

Palp Photo ASD

Ariadna corticola male from Irene Photo Peter Webb

Palp after Lawrence (1952)

Front leg after Lawrence (1952)

Ariadna corticola (continued)

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no known threats to the species. It is protected in the Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve (Foord et al. 2016), Tembe Elephant Park (Haddad et al. 2010) and Ophathe Game Reserve (Haddad & Dippenaar-Schoeman 2015) and Kruger National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2020) and Ndumo Game Reserve (Haddad 2016)

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised, known from both sexes. Carapace and mouth-parts blackish-brown, almost black; posterior apex of sternum a little lighter. Abdomen light to dark brown with an olive green tinge. Leg I dark. Male colour in general paler than in the female; carapace and mandibles brown; sternum and labium reddish-brown; legs yellow-brown, the apex of femur, patella and tibia of leg I darker with an olive tinge; patella and tibia of II darker than femur but lighter than the darker segments of leg I; metatarsus I seen from below as a strong sigmoid curve; abdomen dark olive brown. Total length 9 mm (Lawrence 1952).

Ariadna corticola male from Irene Photo Peter Webb

Ariadna corticola female from Irene Photo Peter Webb

Ariadna dentigera Purcell, 1904

COMMON NAME: Cape Tube-Web Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Western Cape endemic described by Purcell (1904) from the Table Mountain National Park (EOO<100 km²; AOO=4 km²; 9 m a.s.l.). The status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species' range. Therefore, listed as Data Deficient for taxonomic reasons.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Western Cape:* Table Mountain (-33.82, 18.48); Kirstenbosch National Botanical Garden (-34.07, 20.45); Hermanus (-34.4, 19.25).

LIFESTYLE: This species lives in tube signal-webs made in variety of habitats. Sampled from the Fynbos Biome.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Threats to the species are unknown but some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species' range. It is protected in Table Mountain National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2021c).

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised, known only from the female. Carapace dark reddish-brown, almost black anteriorly, with iridescent sheen, the margins finely blackened; chelicera black, with strong iridescent sheen (in spirits); abdomen pale yellow below, brown between the pulmonary opercula, the dorsal surface dark; legs and sternum reddish-brown, the anterior legs slightly more reddish distally but without dorsal markings. Total length 13.5 mm (Purcell 1904).

Ariadna dentigera female from Hermanus Photo Victor Hamilton-Attwell

Tube-web in burned Proteaceae seeds

***Ariadna gryllotalpa* (Purcell, 1904)**

COMMON NAME: Yellow Tube-Web Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Western Cape endemic described by Purcell (1904) as *Segestriella gryllotalpa* and known only from type locality Stompneus, St Helena Bay (EOO<100 km²; AOO=4 km²; 109 m a.s.l.). The status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species' range. Therefore, listed as Data Deficient for taxonomic reasons.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Western Cape*: Stompneus (-32.77, 18.03).

LIFESTYLE: This species lives in tube signal-webs that are made in crevices of walls, rocks, fallen tree trunks or bark of trees in the Fynbos Biome.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Threats to the species are unknown and more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species' range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised, known only from the female. Carapace brownish red, yellowish at the sides posteriorly and at hind margin, with some radiating infusate marks, the head dark reddish-brown to nearly black. Abdomen pale yellowish, with the following purplish-black markings; a band crossing anterior end above the pedicle and extending backwards down each side to middle. Legs pale, second pair infusate on dorsal surface of femur, apex of tibia, basal half and apex of metatarsus and distal half of tarsus; the first pair darker, with brown tibia, infusate as in the second pair; coxae pale yellowish; sternum yellow. Total length 10.25 mm (Purcell. 1904).

Ariadna hottentotta Purcell, 1908

COMMON NAME: Kamaggas Tube-Web Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South Africa endemic described by Purcell (1908) from Kamaggas in the Northern Cape. The species presently is known from three provinces (EOO=37 919 km²; AOO=16 km²; 1212-1513 m a.s.l.). Although the species is presently known only from one sex it has a wide geographical range and can therefore be listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Mountain Zebra National Park (-32.24, 25.43); Asante Game Reserve (-32.282, 24.98); Hogsback (-32.59, 26.92). **Northern Cape:** Kamaggas (-29.75, 17.4). **Western Cape:** Karoo National Park (-32.28, 22.46).

LIFESTYLE: This species lives in tube signal-webs that are made in crevices of walls, rocks, fallen tree trunks or bark of trees. Sampled from the Nama Karoo, Succulent and Grassland biomes (Haddad et al. 2013).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no known threats to the species but some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species' range. It is protected in the Karoo National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman 1999), Mountain Zebra National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2006) and Asante Game Reserve.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised, known only from the female. Colour reddish yellow, the cephalothorax darkened on the side of the head anteriorly, the two posterior pair of legs somewhat paler, the two distal segment of the first pair more reddish; tibia I often with a dark spot above and another on each side at apex; metatarsus I darkened at apex and often on the sides at the base as well; abdomen pale-yellowish (or more or less discoloured), with a broad dorsal band of purplish-black extending from end to end; chelicera dark-red to reddish black. Total length 8.5 mm (Purcell 1908).

Ariadna hottentotta female from Hogsback
Photo Leon Lotz

Ariadna insularis Purcell, 1908

COMMON NAME: Namibia Tube-Web Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A southern African species described by Purcell (1908) from Possession Island, Namibia. In South Africa it is only recorded from the Northern Cape (EOO=2 591 km²; AOO=16 km²; 63-250 m a.s.l.). Although the species is presently known only from one sex it has a wide geographical range and is therefore listed as Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Namibia, South Africa (new record).

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: Northern Cape: Namaqua National Park (-30.0109, 17.5797); Soebatsfontein (-30.11, 17.59); Richtersveld Transfrontier National Park (-28.25, 17.17); Sendelingsdrif (-28.13,16.90).

LIFESTYLE: This species lives in tube signal-webs that are made in crevices of walls, rocks, fallen tree trunks or bark of trees. Sampled from the Desert, Nama Karoo and Succulent Karoo biomes.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no known threats to the species but some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species' range. It is protected in the Namaqua National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2020a) and Richtersveld Transfrontier National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2020b).

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised, known only from the female. Cephalothorax dark mahogany-brown, the head blackish at the side; legs reddish-yellow, the two anterior pairs more reddish distally, all of them more or less infuscate in places, especially on the anterior sides of the femora, patellae and tibiae, the outer (anterior) side of the fourth pair appearing thus more strongly blackened than the outer (posterior) sides of the three anterior pairs; abdomen pale yellowish, the posterior region all round, a broad mesial dorsal area and the area between the first pair of lung-opercula purplish-black; sternum more or less infuscate, darker than the coxae. Total length 14 mm (Purcell 1908).

Ariadna insularis from Namaqua National Park
Photo ASD

Ariadna jubata Purcell, 1904

COMMON NAME: Tsabis Tube-Web Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Northern Cape endemic described by Purcell (1904) from Tsabis. Sampled from several localities (EOO=40 860 km²; AOO=16 km²; 250-1155 m a.s.l.). Although the species is presently known only from one sex it has a wide geographical range and is therefore listed as Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Northern Cape:* Steinkopf (-29.25, 17.73); Richtersveld Transfrontier National Park (-28.25, 17.17); Tswalu Kalahari Reserve (-27.30, 22.44); 20 miles NE of Concordia (-29.53, 17.94).

LIFESTYLE: This species lives in tube signal-webs that are made in crevices of walls, rocks, fallen tree trunks or bark of trees. Males were found under stones in the Desert and Succulent Karoo biomes.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no known threats to the species. It is protected in the Richtersveld Transfrontier National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2020) and Tswalu Kalahari Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2018). More sampling is needed to sample the male of the species.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised, known only from the female. Carapace light brown, the cephalic portion darkened on each side in front, veined with black posteriorly in one specimen; chelicera dark reddish-brown. Posterior pairs of legs pale ochraceous, not at all or only faintly infuscated, the anterior pairs reddish-yellow or reddish, infuscated at least on the under surface and on distal part of inner surface of femora and on distal part of upper side of tibiae along the median line. Abdomen purplish-black, with narrow mark posteriorly below. Sternum and labium brownish-yellow, the latter dark brown on each side. Total length 9.5 mm (Purcell 1904).

Ariadna jubata from Tswalu Nature Reserve immature
Photo Peter Webb

Ariadna karrooica Purcell, 1904

COMMON NAME: Hanover Tube-Web Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described by Purcell (1904) from type locality Hanover. The species has been sampled from three provinces (EOO=185 300 km²; AOO=24 km²; 7-1645m a.s.l.). Due to the wide geographical range, the species is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Eastern Cape:* Port Elizabeth (-33.95, 25.61). *Free State:* Wyndford Guest Farm, Fouriesburg (-28.7, 28.24). *Northern Cape:* Benfontein Nature Reserve (-28.82, 24.82); Eierfontein (-31.06, 24.4); Hanover (-30.94, 24.53); Tswalu Kalahari Reserve (-27.30, 22.44).

LIFESTYLE: This species lives in tube signal-webs that are made in crevices of walls, rocks, fallen tree trunks or bark of trees. Sampled from the Grassland, Nama Karoo, Savanna (Foord et al. 2011) and Thicket biomes.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no known threats to the species. It is protected in Benfontein Nature Reserve and Tswalu Kalahari Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2018)

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised, known from both sexes. Colour of carapace and legs as in the darkest specimens of *A. bilineata*, but the anterior metatarsi dark reddish or almost black. Abdomen pallid, more or less suffused with purplish, at least on the dorsal and ventral surfaces, the middle of the epigastric area and sometimes a couple of posterior ventral patches dark purplish. Sternum and labium deep blackish-brown, the labium sometimes paler at apex. Total length female 10 mm, male 7.5 mm (Purcell 1904).

Male palp after Purcell (1904)

Ariadna karrooica male from Wyndford Guest Farm Photo Peter Webb

***Ariadna kolbei* Purcell, 1904**

COMMON NAME: Kentani Tube-Web Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An Eastern Cape endemic described by Purcell (1904) and known only from the type locality Kentani (EOO<100 km²; AOO=4 km²; 485 m a.s.l.). The status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species' range. Therefore, listed as Data Deficient for taxonomic reasons.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Eastern Cape*: Kentani (-32.5, 28.32).

LIFESTYLE: This species lives in tube signal-webs that are made in crevices of walls, rocks, fallen tree trunks or bark of trees in the Thicket Biome.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no known threats to the species but some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species' range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised, known from only the female. Carapace dark reddish-brown, very dark anteriorly. Chelicera black. Posterior legs rufescent, the anterior legs reddish, the first pair dark red, with lighter patella. Abdomen pallid, suffused with dark purplish above, especially posteriorly. Sternum yellowish-brown. Labium dark brown. Total length 14.25 mm (Purcell 1904)

Ariadna lightfooti Purcell, 1904

COMMON NAME: Pale-footed Tube-Web Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described by Purcell (1904) from Caledon in the Western Cape. The species has been sampled from three provinces (EOO=362 036 km²; AOO=28 km²; 224-1162 m a.s.l.). Although the species is presently known only from one sex it has a wide geographical range and can therefore be listed as Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Addo Elephant National Park (-33.3434, 25.7391). **Northern Cape:** Kamaggas (-29.75, 17.4); Tswalu Kalahari Reserve (-27.30, 22.45). **Western Cape:** Beaufort West Farm Bokvlei (-32.43, 22.35); Beaufort West, Farm Eerste Water (-32.61, 22.81); Beaufort West, Farm Katdoornkuil (-32.709, 22.75); Hermanuspetersfontein, Caledon (-34.24, 19.43).

LIFESTYLE: This species lives in tube signal-webs that are made in crevices of walls, rocks, fallen tree trunks or bark of trees. Sampled from the Fynbos, Nama Karoo and Succulent Karoo biomes.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no known threats to the species. It is protected in the Addo Elephant National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2020) and Tswalu Kalahari Reserve.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised, known from only the female. Carapace pale yellowish, with black hairs, lightly infuscated at the sides posteriorly, the margins finely blackened. Legs pale yellowish, femora, patellae and tibia more or less infuscated on the sides. Chelicerae yellowish. Abdomen purplish-black, with narrow yellow line on each side, the epigastric area, excepting the black transverse patch in front of vulva, pallid. Sternum black. Labium and coxae pale yellowish, narrowly blackened at the tips. Total Length 11 mm (Purcell 1904).

Ariadna lightfooti male Photo ASD

***Ariadna scabripes* Purcell, 1904**

COMMON NAME: Karoo Tube-Web Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Northern Cape endemic described by Purcell (1904) and known only from the type locality Hanover (EOO<100 km²; AOO=4 km²; 1358 m a.s.l.). The status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species range. Therefore, listed as Data Deficient for taxonomic reasons.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Northern Cape*: Hanover (-30.94, 24.53).

LIFESTYLE: This species lives in tube signal-webs that are made in crevices of walls, rocks, fallen tree trunks or bark of trees. Sampled from the Nama Karoo Biome.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Threats to the species are unknown but some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised, known from the female. Carapace yellow, its lateral margins not blackened, the cephalic portion paler behind, brown at the sides and in front and blackened at the anterior margin, at least laterally. Chelicera brown or brownish-yellow, black at apex. Abdomen pallid, or the upper surface more or less suffused with dark purplish, the ventral surface with a pair of purplish patches posteriorly and sometimes one before the vulva. Legs almost uniformly pale yellowish, the anterior tarsi often darker than the other segments, which are without infuscated marks. Coxae and sternum pale yellowish, the latter sometimes partly purplish; labium mostly infuscated at base, pale yellowish at apex. Total length of largest female 9.75 mm (Purcell 1907).

***Ariadna segestrioides* Purcell, 1904**

COMMON NAME: Dunbrody Tube-Web Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An Eastern Cape endemic described by Purcell (1904) and known only from the type locality Dunbrody (EOO<100 km²; AOO=4 km²; 66 m a.s.l.). The status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species' range. Therefore, listed as Data Deficient for taxonomic reasons.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Eastern Cape:* Dunbrody (-33.47, 25.55).

LIFESTYLE: This species lives in tube signal-webs that are made in crevices of walls, rocks, fallen tree trunks or bark of trees. Sampled from the Thicket Biome.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Threats to the species are unknown but some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species' range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised, known from the female. Carapace blackish-brown, slightly paler in the middle. Chelicera reddish-black. Legs blackish-brown to nearly black, the two posterior pairs paler distally, their tarsi, and, to a lesser extent, their metatarsi, pale yellowish, the two anterior pairs of tarsi reddish. Abdomen pallid, with a median series of purplish spots above, the under surface faintly suffused with purplish and with a dark purplish patch posteriorly before the spinners. Sternum and labium blackish-brown. Total length 10.75 mm (Purcell 1904).

***Ariadna similis* Purcell, 1908**

COMMON NAME: Mafikeng Tube-Web Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A North West endemic described by Purcell (1908) and known only from the type locality Mafikeng (EOO<100 km²; AOO=4 km²; 1289 m a.s.l.). The status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species' range. Therefore, listed as Data Deficient for taxonomic reasons.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *North West*: Mafikeng (-25.82, 25.63).

LIFESTYLE: This species lives in tube signal-webs that are made in crevices of walls, rocks, fallen tree trunks or bark of trees. Sampled from the Savanna Biome.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Threats to the species are unknown but some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species' range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised, known from the female. Resemble *A. bilineata* but larger and colour darker. Carapace reddish-yellow to dark reddish-brown, darker anteriorly; surface hairy and usually finely veined with black; chelicera yellowish-red to black. Abdomen with a fine, pale line running from end to end down middle. Legs faintly or strongly infuscated, the anterior pairs darker than the posterior. Total length 11.5 mm (Purcell 1908).

Ariadna umtalica Purcell, 1904

COMMON NAME: Zimbabwe Tube-Web Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A southern African endemic described by Purcell (1904) from Zimbabwe. The species is recorded from three southern African countries. In South Africa known only from Northern Cape and Gauteng. Although the species is presently known only from one sex it has a wide geographical range in Africa and can therefore be listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Zimbabwe, Botswana and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Gauteng:** Irene (field opposite Gem Village) (-25.89, 28.23). **Northern Cape:** Kuruman (-27.46, 23.43).

LIFESTYLE: This species lives in tube signal-webs that are made in crevices of walls, rocks, fallen tree trunks or bark of trees. Males were found under stones in the Savanna Biome (Foord et al. 2011).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no known threats to the species.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised, known only from the female, not illustrated. Carapace dark brown, the ocular area black; chelicera reddish-black; abdomen pallid, suffused with purplish; legs infuscated as in dark specimens of *A. bilineata*, with two posterior pairs, reddish-ochraceous the anterior tibia and metatarsus blackish-red; sternum and labium brown, the latter paler at apex. Total length 12 mm (Purcell 1904).

Ariadna umtalica from Irene Photo Peter Webb

UNDETERMINED SPECIES

Plettenberg

Cederberg Wilderness Area

Tussen die rivier

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